

Editorial

Mpox – A Persistent Global Health Challenge

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Received:: August 16, 2024 | Accepted:: September 20, 2024 | Published: October 26, 2024

Monkeypox (Mpox), a viral zoonosis, has emerged as a global public health threat since its initial discovery in the 1950s. Although it was first identified in laboratory monkeys, the disease was later found in humans, with the first cases reported in the Democratic Republic of the Congo in 1970. However, in May 2022, the World Health Organization (WHO) began receiving reports of an increase in Mpox cases in non-endemic countries. In light of this situation and the spread of the disease, the WHO declared the outbreak a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC), raising the level of attention and recommending enhanced surveillance capacities and public health measures to contain its transmission in affected countries.

Epidemiology and Transmission

The epidemiology of Mpox is complex, involving interactions between animal hosts and humans. Studies indicate that rodents, such as *Cricetomys gambianus* and *Graphiurus* spp., may act as natural reservoirs of the virus [1]. Transmission to humans can occur through direct contact with the blood, bodily fluids, or lesions of infected animals. In humans, person-to-person transmission is possible, primarily through respiratory droplets during prolonged face-to-face contact or direct contact with contaminated materials such as bedding [2].

As of September 3, 2024, a total of 64,669 confirmed cases of Mpox have been reported worldwide, including 146 deaths across 32 countries and territories in the Region of the Americas. In total, 57,571 cases and 115 deaths were recorded in 2022, 4,077 cases and 28 deaths in 2023, and 3,021 cases and three deaths so far in 2024 [3].

Current Reality and Public Health Responses

The recent 2022 outbreak, which affected multiple countries across different continents, demonstrated the ability of the Mpox virus to adapt and persist outside its traditional endemic zones. This outbreak highlighted gaps in global health systems, particularly in early detection and rapid response to emerging diseases. As of July 2023, more than 70,000 cases had been reported in approximately 100 countries, with the majority of cases reported among men who have sex with men (MSM), raising important questions about stigma and equity in healthcare access [4].

The international response included the use of vaccines previously developed for human smallpox, given the similarities between the two viruses, as well as awareness campaigns and isolation protocols. However, significant challenges remain, including the need for faster diagnostics, specific treatments, and more comprehensive vaccination strategies [5].

Call for Manuscript Submissions

Biomedinar invites researchers and healthcare professionals to submit original articles, reviews, and case reports addressing clinical, epidemiological, immunological, virological, and social aspects of Mpox. We particularly welcome studies exploring new approaches to diagnosis, treatment, prevention, as well as analyses of public health policy responses in different geographic contexts. Submissions will undergo a rigorous peer-review process, ensuring the publication of high-quality research that can contribute to the

advancement of knowledge and control of this significant disease.

Interested authors should submit their manuscripts to: biomedinar@gmail.com

Further information on author guidelines can be found on our official website.

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